

EDITORIAL

Resources Management and Future: Welcome to the Sustainable Resources Management Journal

Mohammad Aljaradin, Editor-in-Chief

Corresponding author email: chief-editor@srwj.se

Sustainable resource management is often defined as the planning and decision making process that seeks to organize and balance the social, economic and environmental demands on resource use to achieve future sustainable benefits.

The future of generation and the quality of life for people today will require standing on the use and consumption of natural resources, including materials, energy and land. Exploring new potentials of using suitable raw material streams for developing new products in close co-operation with the concerned sectors is significantly important. Most things that we produce end up at a landfill; our planet has limited amounts of resources. The current ways of producing and consuming products have therefore led to problems such as climate change, a decrease of available resources and pollution of our air, soil and water. The wise use of our resources is important to the environment and existence.

The sustainable use and management of natural resources have therefore come into focus and has been the subject of many policy discussions over more than a decade, beginning with the summit in Rio de Janeiro in 1992.

Sustainable Resources Management Journal (SRMJ) is an International, peer-reviewed, interdisciplinary, monthly, and fully refereed journal accepting original and high-quality articles covering a wide range of topics in scientific research, dedicated to promoting high standards and excellence in the creation and dissemination of scientific knowledge.

Sustainable Resources Management Journal has been launched to help meet the growing need for publications that foster productive discussions between researchers, and permit exchanging ideas related to sustainable resources management, in a manner that benefits both the research community and decision makers.

The primary aim of the Journal is to raise environmental awareness and provide high quality information. As an interdisciplinary scholarly journal, with a scope on all aspects of natural science: water resources management, sustainability of water resources, ground and surface water, water use and reuse, desalination, sustainable waste management, recycling and waste to energy.

Sustainable Resources Management Journal aim to bring important work to a wide international audience and therefore only publish papers with strong messages that advance our understanding in the field. Both experimental and theoretical studies are accepted, as are descriptive or historical accounts, although these must offer insights into issues of general interest.

Sustainable Resources Management Journal is an open access journal that publishes papers submitted in English language. **SRMJ** welcomes author submission of original and significant contributions. **SRMJ** accept: research papers; working papers; short communications; case studies and literature surveys.

Articles submitted should not have been previously published or be currently under consideration for publication in any journal and should only present original unpublished research results. Figure 1 present the publication progress at **SRMJ**.

Figure 1: the publication progress at SRMJ.